

Determination of Nickel(II) by Atomic Absorption Spectrometry by Adsorption of its 1-Hydroxy-1,3-diphenyl-2-thiourea Complex on Microcrystalline Naphthalene

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The hydroxy substituted thioureas have extensive analytical applications as a spectrophotometric and gravimetric reagent for a large number of metal ions¹. In present investigation a new more sensitive and selective organic reagent, viz. 1-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyl-2-thiourea has been selected as a complexing agent for the determination of nickel(II) by atomic absorption spectrometry. The reagent reacts with nickel(II) to form a stable water-insoluble complex. The complexation between hydroxy substituted thioureas and metal ions is attributed to the availability of the oxime and thio-keto groups. The introduction of oxime group in such compounds influences the distribution coefficients; pH of precipitation of the metal oximates and molar extinction coefficients. 1-Hydroxy-1,3-diphenyl-2-thiourea-nickel complex is readily adsorbed on microcrystalline naphthalene in aqueous phase. The adsorbed mixture of the complex with naphthalene was separated from aqueous phase by filtration, dried and dissolved in dimethylformamide. The absorbance was measured at 232 nm against similarly prepared reagent blank by atomic absorption spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

Nickel(II) complex with 1-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyl-2-thiourea was obtained according to the recommended procedure (see Experimental). For complete adsorption of the complex 3.5 ml naphthalene

solution is enough. Adsorption is very fast at 40–50°. Maximum absorbance was obtained in the pH range 2.5–5.0. Ten samples of the solution containing 5.0 µg of nickel(II) were prepared by the recommended procedure, providing a mean absorbance of 0.154 with a relative standard deviation of 0.85%. Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration range 0.5–5.2 µg of nickel(II) solution in 10 ml dimethylformamide solution. The sensitivity is found to be 0.0161 µg cm⁻² for 1% absorption. The proposed method was applied to the determination of nickel in steel alloys (EN-36A, EN-24 containing nickel : certified value 3.26 and 1.60%; obtained 3.26 ± 0.08 and 1.58 ± 0.03% nickel respectively). The results show that the values are in the good agreement with the certified values.

Effect of diverse metal ions : Possible interferences due to the presence of various diverse ions were observed into the solution of nickel(II) complex of 1-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyl-2-thiourea containing 5.0 µg of nickel(II) (tolerance limit in paranthesis) : Sb^{III} (150 µg), Co^{II} (200 µg), Ti^{IV} (300 µg), V^V (400 µg), Zn^{II} and Pd^{II} (1 µg), Cu^{II} (1.5 µg), Fe^{III} and Bi^{III} (2 µg), Pd^{II} (4 µg), Cd^{II} (4.5 µg), Cr^{VI} (5 µg), Mo^{VI} (10 µg), Mn^{II} (140 µg) and Al^{III} (200 µg). EDTA and KCN interfered seriously because of the formation of more stable complex (masking agent).

This proposed method is quantitative, selective,

free from interferences having low limit of detection due to organic solvent which enhances absorbance of the complex two folds compared to aqueous phase. The method has been successfully applied for the determination of nickel in steel sample with satisfactory results.

Experimental

Standard stock nickel solution (100 ppm) was prepared by dissolving high purity nickel wire (0.1 g) in 1 : 1 nitric acid (5 ml) and diluted to 1 dm³ with distilled water. Stock solution was further diluted as required. A 0.2% solution of 1-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyl-2-thiourea was prepared in ethanol. A 20% naphthalene solution was prepared in acetone. Buffer solution was prepared by mixing equal volume of 1 M acetic acid and 1 M ammonium acetate for pH 4.0.

All chemicals used were of spectrograde quality. A Perkin-Elmer 2380 atomic absorption spectrometer was used for all absorbance measurements. pH measurements were made with a Systronics 335 pH meter.

Procedure : Standard sample solution containing 0.5–5.2 µg of nickel(II) was diluted with distilled water to 50.0 ml. The pH of the solution

was adjusted to 4.0 by adding acetate buffer (2.5 ml) and a 0.2% 1-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyl-2-thiourea solution (2.0 ml) was added. The contents were mixed thoroughly and heated on water-bath at 50° for 10 min. Then 20% naphthalene solution (3.5 ml) was added to it and shaken vigorously for 90 s. The nickel(II) complex was adsorbed on microcrystalline naphthalene. It was filtered off, washed with distilled water, dried and the solid mass was dissolved in dimethylformamide (10 ml). The solution was aspirated into air-acetylene flame and the absorbance value was measured at 232 nm using a nickel hollow cathode lamp as a light source by AAS against similarly prepared reagent blank.

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